

NanOx4EStor

Nanoscaled ferroelectric (pseudo)-binary oxide thin film supercapacitors for flexible and ultrafast pulsed power electronics

At a Glance

Funded under: M-ERA.NET3

Overall budget: € 642.822,00

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Coordinated by: University of Minho, Portugal

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The Project

The main goal of the **NanOx4EStor** project is to develop innovative and cost effective high-throughput technologies for the fabrication of advanced supercapacitors based on wake-up free (pseudo)-binary oxide thin films, fabricated by physical vapour deposition (PVD) processes, with optimized ferroelectric and energy storage (ES) properties through (i) strain, (ii) interface and (iii) dead-layer engineering.

Consortium

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Dissemination

Project website:

<https://inl.cnrs.fr/projects/nanox4estor/>

LinkedIn Group

<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/9260371/>

ResearchGate

<https://www.researchgate.net/project/Nanoscaled-ferroelectric-pseudo-binary-oxide-thin-film-supercapacitors-for-flexible-and-ultrafast-pulsed-power-electronics>

Publications

14. Grégoire Magagnin, Martine Le Berre, Sara Gonzalez, Brice Gautier, Damien Deleruyelle, Bertrand Vilquin, Jordan Bouaziz, An Original Positive-Up-Negative-Down Protocol for Electrical Characterization of Antiferroelectric Materials, *Nano Lett.* 25, 16, 6686–6692 (2025).

13. J. S. Kim, N. Strkalj, A. Silva, V. Lenzi, L. Marques, M. O. Hill, Z. Yuan, Y.-X. Liu, M. T. Becker, S. M. Fairclough, C. Ducati, Y. Zhang, J. Shen, Z. Hu, H. Dou, H. Wang, J. P. B. Silva, J. L. MacManus-Driscoll, “Coercive field control in epitaxial ferroelectric $\text{Hf}_{0.5}\text{Zr}_{0.5}\text{O}_2$ thin films by nanostructure engineering”, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 17, 17, 25442–25450 (2025).

Conference presentations and proceedings

37. Grégoire Magagnin, Martine Le Berre, Sara Gonzalez, Damien Deleruyelle, Bertrand Vilquin, and Jordan Bouaziz, "Antiferroelectric PUND measurements on ZrO_2 ", Novel High-k Application Workshop 2025, NaMLab GmbH, Dresden, Germany, March 12-13, 2025.

36. Veniero Lenzi, Alexandre Silva, José P. B. Silva, Luís Marques, “Understanding the role of strain, stress, defects and dopants in the ferroelectric, switching and phase stability properties of epitaxial hafnia and zirconia films.”, 2025 MRS Spring Meeting & Exhibit, Symposium EL08-Ferroc Materials and Heterostructures, Seattle, USA, April 7-11, 2025

35. Nuno E. Silva, Ampattu R. Jayakrishnan, Adrian Kaim, Katarzyna Gwozdz, J. S. Kim, Mario Pereira, Luís Marques, Robert L. Z. Hoyer, Judith L. MacManus-Driscoll, José P. B. Silva, “Ferroelectric oxide thin films as a promising route for self-powered photodetection” 2025 MRS Spring Meeting & Exhibit, Symposium EL16—Nanogenerators and Piezotronics, Seattle, USA, April 7-11, 2025.

34. I. Fina, T. Song, H. Tan, T. Zakusylo, A. Quintana, N. Dix, P. Koutsogiannis, J. L. Ortola, J. Lyu, S. Estandía, J. Sort, C. Magén, J.A. Pardo, V. Lenzi, L. Marques, J. Silva, F. Sánchez, “Ferroelectric hafnia: an opportunity for next-generation memory devices”, GEFES 2025 Conference, Oviedo, Spain, January 29-31, 2025.

33. N. E. Silva, A. R. Jayakrishnan, A. Kaim, K. Gwozdz, J. S. Kim, M. C. Istrate, C. Ghica, M. Pereira, L. Marques, R. L. Z. Hoyer, J. L. MacManus-Driscoll, J. P. B. Silva, “Ferroelectric $\text{Hf}_x\text{Zr}_{1-x}\text{O}_2$ thin films for self-powered healthcare applications”. Novel High-k Application Workshop 2025, NaMLab GmbH, Dresden, Germany, March 12-13, 2025.

PhD thesis defence

Mr. Cosmin Marian ISTRATE, member of the NIMP research team (Romania), defended his PhD thesis “Structural and spectroscopic information in nanostructured materials” on 21st of October, 2025, at the University of Bucharest, based on microstructural investigations performed by advanced analytical transmission electron microscopy techniques on ferroelectric thin films within the NanOx4EStor project.

Coercive field control in rhombohedrally distorted orthorhombic (r-d o) $\text{Hf}_{0.5}\text{Zr}_{0.5}\text{O}_2$ (HZO) films

Low laser fluence, which produces a higher proportion of (111) orientation and high crystallinity, leads to a roughly 30% reduction in coercive field compared to literature values on the r-d o-phase HZO films. Overall, this work shows the importance of controlling nanostructure to tune the ferroelectric properties of HZO films, enabling performance optimization of hafnia for memory devices. Find out more about these very exciting results in: J. S. Kim, et al. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 17, 17, 25442–25450 (2025).

Original positive up negative down (PUND) protocol intended to accurately investigate the energy storage behavior in antiferroelectric (AFE) thin-films

The current work provides a crucial framework for advancing the study of AFE materials. Beyond these immediate improvements, the AFE-PUND method lays the groundwork for the more advanced characterization of AFE materials. Such developments are vital for optimizing ZrO_2 -based nanosupercapacitors and broadening their application in next-generation energy storage devices. Find out more about these very exciting results in: G. Magagnin, et al. *Nano Lett.* 25, 16, 6686–6692 (2025).